

34 To explore various regulatory points in the stress response, we optimized the stress
35 conditions to capture different response times. Consequently, different treatment
36 intervals were sampled, always at the same time of day and right after stress exposure:
37 before stress (control, C); the first day of heat stress without drought (T-1, first day); and
38 the first, second, third, fourth, and fifth days of combined heat-drought stress (T1, T2,
39 T3, T4, T5; from the second to the sixth day). After the combined stress period, control
40 conditions were re-established, and recovery was monitored at two- and seven-days
41 post-stress (R2 and R7) (**Figure 1**). Chlorophyll fluorescence was measured at each
42 point for monitoring.

43 Following the first combined stress assay (E1, September 2022), the plants were split
44 into two groups to assess 6-month and 1-year memory. A parallel control group
45 consisting of plants of the same age but never exposed to stress was also maintained
46 (**Figure 1**). The second combined stress assay (E2, February 2023) was conducted on
47 1.5-year-old seedlings, and the third combined stress assay (E3, September 2023) was
48 conducted on 2-year-old seedlings. This approach allowed for comparison of pine
49 seedlings of the same age, but with different exposure histories (two stress exposures
50 versus one), to evaluate memory maintenance effects over distinct recovery periods (6
51 or 12 months). For each experiment and memory group, plants were divided into three
52 to five biological replicates, with each replicate consisting of needles from three plants.
53 The same individuals were used for the entire experiment. All samples were promptly
54 frozen in liquid nitrogen and stored at -80°C until biochemical analyses were performed.

55 Physiological characterization

56 To evaluate stress damage on photosynthetic process, chlorophyll fluorescence was
57 measured before sampling each treatment interval (C, T-1, T1, T2, T3, T4, T5, R2, R7)
58 employing a fluorometer (OS1p-FL, Opti-Sciences, USA) and pre-exposing needles to
59 dark conditions for 20 minutes to obtain maximum quantum efficiency of photosystem II
60 (PSII) (F_v/F_m).

61 Physiological evaluation of different groups of memory plants was performed on C, T1,
62 T3 and T5 treatment times. Extraction and quantification of molecular metabolism
63 markers (Chlorophyll a, Chlorophyll b, Carotenoids, Malondialdehyde (MDA), Free
64 Amino Acids (FAA), Total Soluble Sugars (TSS), Starch (STA), Total Flavonoids (TFL),
65 and Total Phenolic Compounds (TPC)) were proceeded according to López-Hidalgo et
66 al. (2021), starting from 10 mg of dry and homogenized needles and an ethanol
67 extraction. Statistical evaluation of those measurements was carried out on R
68 programming language (v.4.1.2) running under RStudio employing agricolae package

69 v.1.3-5 (one-way ANOVA with post-hoc Tukey HSD for parametric variables and Kruskal-
70 Wallis with post-hoc Dunn test when non-parametric variables) (p-value < 0.05).

71 Figure Legends

72 **Figure 1. Experimental Design and Physiology Overview.** From top to bottom: stress
73 memory diagram with circles indicating sampling points; heat-drought stress
74 experimental design with circles indicating sampling points; Phase I (September 2022),
75 Phase II (February 2023, 6-month memory), and Phase III (September 2023, 1-year
76 memory) soil moisture percentage (SM%) and chlorophyll fluorescence (Fv/Fm). %
77 Stress = soil moisture at the end of the stress period. % Watering = soil moisture after
78 watering to maintain the specified soil moisture range following the temperature ramp-
79 down and before the night period. E1 = Plants with two combined stress exposures.
80 E2/E3 = Plants with one combined stress exposure. Different letters indicate significant
81 differences for the same plant group (E1, E2, E3) across treatments. Asterisks denote
82 significant differences between plant groups for the same treatment. n.s = non-
83 significant. Data from Phase III and E3 plants are pending to be plotted.

● Control ● Heat Stress ● Heat x Drought Stress

